

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE TREATMENT IN BASAL CELL CANCER

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Abstract

Treatment of BCC is essential due to tissue invasion, aggressive impact on the skin and the low but existing risk of tumor dissemination, estimated between 0.002% and 0.5%[1]. Factors such as the patient's age, medical history, number of lesions, severity of the condition and ability to adapt to treatment also play an important role in the therapeutic decision[1]. The main goal of treatment is complete excision of the tumor. Other treatment modalities include cryotherapy, immunomodulatory drugs, laser treatment, or topical chemotherapeutic agents. Given the slow growth of these tumors, according to European Association of Dermato-Oncology less invasive treatments may be preferred in elderly patients, even if this entails a higher risk of recurrence. Cystic and nodular BCCs have well-defined borders, while morphoeic, micronodular, trabecular, infiltrative, and basosquamous types have less distinct borders, giving them increased virulence. Given the superficial invasion, topical treatments could be effective in superficial BCCs.

Keywords: basal cell carcinoma, surgical treatment, cryotherapy treatment.

Introduction. Basal cell carcinoma is a low-grade skin tumor that begins in the epidermal basal layer and invades the surrounding tissues. It is slow growing, locally aggressive and rarely metastasizes[3]. Epidemiological study of BCC is complicated to perform accurately, because systemic monitoring is often not performed by oncology registries, and not all cases of BCC are sent for histopathological evaluation. In the Republic of Moldova, among the most common malignant tumors are: breast, colorectal, prostate, skin and trachea cancer, which represents 52.6% of the total number of malignant tumors. Non-melanoma skin cancer in 2021 was detected in 883 people, and in 2022 it increased to 979 [2]. Treatment of basal cell carcinoma is essential because of invasion into adjacent tissues, aggressive impact on the skin, and the low but existing risk of tumor dissemination, estimated at 0.002% to 0.5%[1]. Factors such as the patient's age, medical history, number of lesions, severity of the condition and ability to adapt to treatment also play an important role in the therapeutic decision[1]. The main goal of treatment is complete excision of the tumor. Other treatment modalities include cryotherapy, immunomodulatory drugs, laser treatment, or topical chemotherapeutic agents [4]. Management can be surgical (standard excision of primary BCC with predetermined margins, Mohs micrographic surgery, curettage with and without cauterization, cryosurgery and laser ablation) as well as non-surgical (radiotherapy, topical Imiquimod 5% cream, topical 5-fluorouracil 5% , photodynamic therapy, in-

tralesional therapy, targeted therapy, electrochemotherapy). Advances in the medical field and the development of tailored therapy have continuously improved the quality and life expectancy of patients. However, it is crucial that people are aware of the symptoms, risk factors and treatment options available in order to intervene promptly and prevent relapses. With adequate treatment, the prognosis for most patients is favorable. The risk of developing a second BCC is 36-50%. Periodic examination, sun protection, consulting a doctor in the early stages is of major importance. [5]

The purpose of the study to analyze the type of treatment in the case of basal cell cancers according to location, size and number.

Materials and methods. The patients in the study were randomly selected, 150 patients from the Skin Tumors and Malignant Melanoma section of the Oncological Institute, grouped into 2 groups, the first group of 75 with BCC who underwent surgical treatment by excision of skin lesions, the second group was formed of 75 patients with BCC treated by cryotherapy. In the study, the treatment methods used in patients with BCC were analyzed, initially it was analyzed CBC treatment by both methods, depending on BCC location.

Results. According to (figure 1), we can see that in the case of patients with BCC, cryotherapy was more frequently applied in the case of localization at the level of the face and in the limb region, and in the case of the application of the treatment by Excision of the lesions it was preferred in the case of localization at the level of the trunk (chest/back reg.).

Figure.1. Distribution of patients according to BCC location depending on the applied treatment.

Later, the histopathological forms of BCC were analyzed depending on the treatment applied, according to the results we can see that cryotherapy treatment was more frequently applied in the case of nodular

(45/74), superficial (13/15) and micronodular (13/17) forms), and excision of the lesions was applied more frequently in the case of infiltrative forms (39/41).

Figure.2. The treatment applied depends on the histopathological form of BCC.

The result and efficiency of the applied treatment largely depends on the postoperative dynamics of the patient and the number of days in the hospital until discharge due to the positive dynamics, the number of days of hospitalization of the patients depending on the applied treatment were analyzed, as we can see (table

1), in most cases were "one-day surgery", with some differences in the application of surgical treatment by excision of skin lesions, in the case of BCC patients with dimensions of 4-5 cm and patients with more than 4-5 BCC injuries or more complicated cases when patients were hospitalized for 2-3 days until discharge.

Table 1

The type of treatment applied	Media + SD (hospitalization days)	The p value
Cryotherapy	1±0,07	p<0,05
Surgical tissue excision	1,3 ±0,28	p<0,05

Conclusions. According to the results, for patients with small-sized BCC, multiple BCC and BCC with well-defined margins, cryotherapy by applying liquid nitrogen is acceptable, especially in BCC on the face and in the region of the upper and lower limbs in order

to sacrifice the tissues to a minimum and preserve aesthetics integumentary, and surgical tissue excision is preferred in the case of BCC >1-2 cm in size, especially the infiltrative forms, and recurrent BCC by applying incisions within the limits of safety oncological.

References

1. Carcinomul bazocelular - factori de risc și strategie terapeutică. [Publicated la 03.03.2021]. In: Medic.ro.
2. ANSP Epidemiological status of skin diseases 2024.
3. Hassan Ashfaq, Peerzada Umar et al Carcinomul bazocelular: diagnostic, management și prevenire J. Mol. Pathol. 2024, 5(2), 153-170.
4. Smith, V.; Walton, S. Treatment of facial basal cell carcinoma: A review. J. Skin Cancer 2011, 380371.
5. Sofroni D, Ghidirim N, Miron L, Sofroni L, Mereuță I, Martalog V et al. Tratat de Oncologie 2020, 348-353.